

Paradoxical Paradox in a Poem Black and White for (Ahmed Matar)

Hassan Ghanem Fadala Al-Janabi

Article Info

Article History

Received:
December 03, 2021

Accepted:
July 04, 2022

Keywords :

Critical Reading,
Phenomenon, Ahmed
Matar

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6792767

Abstract

Critical reading of the poetic text varies according to the goal that you aim for, and there is a qualitative difference for reading, some of which "bites the entire poetic text and does not limit itself to the thresholds of its central truth ... And among them, what you find its mission ends with defining the great truth in the poetic text" (1) and to understand the work Literary understanding is real, it must move in its treatment at two levels that represent both sides of the internal and external approach to the study of that work (2), without this type of treatment cannot provide a procedural perception that accommodates all the textual and contextual variations and contradictory, within the literary work under study (3).

If we return to the phenomenon of opposites as a stylistic technique, we find that its poetry depends to a large extent on the effectiveness of combining two opposing elements in a particular syntactic manner, and this contrast is in response to the pressure of the joint dictionary on the special behavior capabilities in a context, which is not interpreted as a deficit (4). Or technical weakness, insofar as it reflects a special possibility to combine structures and height with their semantic performance (5).

Therefore, the contrast represents one of the stylistic options that express the movement (6) arising from its acceptance that two moral shipments coexist within (the consciousness room) (7) although they represent two information, one is negative and the other is positive, and from the interaction of these two information/ semantic values, the resulting emotional influence is characterized by It has the language of poetry (8).

Our reading of the text (white and black) by the poet Ahmed Matar is neutral reading, so it seeks to be free to choose the procedures for critical treatment of the text, while keen to hold it accountable faithfully for its technical and moral values first and foremost, it seeks to reveal the creative approaches to producing the text and what is conducive Mechanisms of semantics.

Introduction

The text (white and black) includes three semi-independent sections, each of which provides treatment for the phenomenon of contradiction as a global phenomenon, in which the poet draws a feature or daily life scene, and that scene is used to perform his active role in shaping the poetic image, and then give it the semantic paradoxes It is interesting to note that the poet did not neglect the intellectual unity of the text, despite the many structural aspects of the text, we find that he uses some stylistic techniques as he investigates the semantic dimensions of the text through the parallel systems and the parallel resolution.

First, the parallel format:

The text overlooks us with the semantic dimension, the paradox-speaking contrast of its title (white black), and this contrast reduces the expression of a conflict between two poles that represent an analogous aspect of the dualities of existence. If we contemplate the contexts of the text and its structures, we find that some of them take parallel paths, including indications that stoke the amazing spirit of paradox in the mind of the recipient, which creates a crack in its principle, visualizing the difference between the two colors (black and white), and then that crack grows and expands as we progress in following Examine text phrases and their structures.

In the first section of the text, we find that he makes a comparison between (the white man and the black man) as two different self. The semantic value of the contrast does not stop at the boundaries of the color difference between them, but extends to cover the specific movement of each of them (the two men) in the battlefield of daily life, which is presented The poet, in the form of pictures drawn in parallel composition with

balanced rhythm, contrast contributes greatly to granting this movement its qualitative dimension, which is revealed by the contextual contrast in the second and fourth poetic lines:

A white man falls asleep cooled in the shadows

A black man is working in the field

Upon careful consideration of the two expressions of the two poetic lines, we find that they involve two opposing semantic shipments that go through two different domains, one of which is negative, expressed in the case of the inactive white man (who falls asleep) isolated (invisible) invisibly in the (shadow), which is passive and parasitic, and the second is What the situation of the present black man (working) present (burnt) clearly expresses in the (field) is clearly positive and productive.

Go to the following lines in the same section:

This black reaps cotton

That white reaps sweat + black

We note that the contradiction extends to include what the names of the reference include in the two elements (attendance and absence) as the element of presence is represented in the name of the sign (this), while the element of absence is represented by the name of the sign (that), and it appears that this use was not free or unaware, but rather I want him to contribute to fulfilling two contrasting images or two contradictory states in the poet's conscience and conscience, as he referred to (Al-Aswad) in the name of the proximity/ presence to confirm his solutions in a place close to the observation of the blind eye, in the midst of the battle of life, while leaving the expression in the name of the sign (that Coupled with (white) who wanted the phrase about his absence, his distance, his drowning in his luxury and his softness with His pleasures, so that the relative (this=black) is out of the attainment circle, despite being the productive actor, and the distant (that=white) is the one who reaps the fruits of the effort despite the fact that he did not exert but rather did not attend at all.

Thus, the poet continues to market his phrases in a parallel way, but he breaks the rhythmic balance by lengthening the last poetic line from the first syllable, as we find that parallelism and equilibrium coincide at the beginning of the two phrases, while the breach of balance occurs in the last line of the passage by adding (black) to (race). This suggests that the total paradox occurs at the end of the passage when the passive is dominant and the positive, the clear and productive product is crushed and distilled, and that is a paradox declared by the parallel pattern before it is announced by the format of the meanings presented by the vocabulary functions.

In the second passage, the poet maintains a parallel arrangement, as we find it introduces the first and second capillary lines of the mentioned passage by the neighbor and the sewer (in our stove / from our stove) then each of the two lines opens an opposite meaning to the other at the level of composition and significance, in the first line the verb presents (burned) Then it is followed by the deputy actor described as (seat coal), while the second line adopts the mechanism of delaying the action (ascending) and introducing the initiator (smoke thread) to disclose a semantic relationship between the two combinations based on cause and effect in the opposite way:

In our stove ... Charcoal burns a seat

From our stove ... a thread of smoke comes up

Burn that..to climb this!

Combustion is a cause for ascension and transcendence, for coal has a present material indication that has boundaries, meaning, and opaque color, and at the end of it it turns into ash in an unhelpful and not worthy secretion, and by that transformation corresponds to another dangerous reversal, as the smoke (white) which is equal to it is sublimated What is the intangible, intangible and inspirational element transformed into the dominant and the present equal to (chaser / graying) in the last section of the text, this means that the present material starting (charcoal = black) is burned and expelled because it is determined by a certain shape and size that does not resist the current, emergency smoke (9), The dominant, uncontrolled boundary because of its gelatinous And its movement and spread, which makes it content of things in an octopus shape capable of surrounding, including and exclusively shining on the rubble of burned charcoal and the remains of its mortal ash; An objective equation for the black man mentioned in the first passage, so replace the reference to it with that burned (coal = black) to denote its annihilation, exclusion, fading and displacement, compared to the second reference (the thread of smoke), which was taken as an objective equation for the white man _ referred to (this = Smoke thread = Al-Abyad) to demonstrate his presence, which was postponed while awaiting the moment of his brilliance and ascension on the ashes of burned charcoal, and then proceeds to conclude this passage with open interrogative phrases unanswered to leave the recipient with the opportunity of diligence and anticipation of all possibilities, so he says:

Who is Al-Saddad for?

Is this white ... or that black one?!

In this way, the indication of the name of the sign is invested in the elements of attendance and absence, attending in this passage is attributed to (white) which is (smoke - rookie = man- master) because they are smoke / the white man shares the exclusivity of each of them for reasons of survival and permanence; while attributing the element of absence to (Al-Aswad) which is (charcoal - burnt = man - black) because each of

them's mouthful pronounces the loss of the causes of permanence and survival, so he lost something that he does not enjoy (10), so how can he give it ?! Therefore, we find that the movement is not limited to the actions mentioned in the context of the first and second sections of the text. Rather, the names of the signal contribute to drawing the graphical line of the function of the movement that took a one-way path based on the color values, starting from black - to white to return that movement In the last section of the text, it is assigned to white as the last controlling element in the survival game ... which we can explain in the following diagram:

Black	White
Snooze	Works
Reap Reap	
Sweat	Cotton
Gray	Boarding – Youth

Annihilation - exclusion - absence of combustion solutions - presence - containment - survival (After consumption).

Thus the poet maintains through these relationships the semantic thread that links the first and second syllables of the text, that thread that represents the connection of the meaning or idea presented at the text level (the idea of exploitation) and the expression of its continuity in revealing the contradictions between (comfort x suffering) and (luxury x Roughness), (Richness x Poverty) (11), (Sacrifice x Substitution) ... etc.

Second: the parallel resolution format:

In the last section of the text, the parallel form is retracted, but is lost between the phrases of the text. He lives) on the described name (black poetry), and he thus invests the narrative (narration) narration of the ability to draw the image and provide it with the semantic and poetic dimensions, as it aims to humanize (poetry) and grant the property of the ability to live, move, act and emotion, so he took (black poetry) An objective equivalent to (the man) in the first pass and the (coal) in the passage The second and their color (black) as the main theme that is animated in the text against the second theme represented in color (white) (12). The black poetry was based on the act of living that was reported in the time of the move indicating a previous presence (was - live), but that life was conditional and governed by the movement (white hair) And his infiltrated arrival is among the folds of invisibility and absence, and he is thus presented as an objective equation (for a man) in the first section and (smoke) in the second part of the text by focusing on their color (white), and from this the idea of coexistence of the opposite opposites coexists unequally. With the ability, not the will, not the result or the bottom line, this coexistence style has neither the possibility of harmony nor stability! Because the movement of (the white) and its activity circle are expanding and solutions / the dominant presence in the place, and in this (white) movement the movement of the lions recedes and narrows towards fading and fading / absence, so it changes accordingly. The map changes (the demography of the place) and it is the result that characterizes the current situation (13), so (white hair) after domination and domination of the place goes to expelling (black hair) and excluding it away from the place, and in that we read:

In my father's head ... Black hair was living
 A day came white hair
 He was not killed or expelled
 But when white increased one day ...
 Black kicked out!

From here we can say: The apparent lack of parallelism in the expressions of the last section of the text tells us the summary of the lack of parallelism and equivalence between the poles of the dialectic of the contrast, and this means that there is an opposition between two different positions, the first is the position of the other, and the coexistence of the other is positive in its essence, While the other is represented by the position of the repellent white of the other (14), it is negative in its essence (15), and here the textualization of the text returns to the beginning, as the black was a productive and sacrificing factor ... etc., while the white was lazy (falls asleep) a negative influence, which is the idea that the text was keen to present from its title To its end, the idea that can be summed up as a wall The negation of the negative leading to the melting of one of the powder poles (black) in the equation, and reducing it to the dominant (white) other, which is the algebraic limb in place (16).

Conclusion

The critical reading of the poetic text varies according to the goal that you aim for, and accordingly, the goal of our reading of the text (white and black) by Ahmed Matar is to find the contrast theme as a central theme that has its presence and its contribution to creating the poetic text and producing its overall significance.

The poet Ahmed Matar has created an authorship between three passages to produce the text (white and black), as these passages appear to be independent in terms of their appearance and their general theme, but when we look closely at them, we reveal to us the central truth represented by the contrast between the two colors (white and black), that contrast The reading horizon opens to two poles jostled in the place. Despite what

is to be presented from the premise of coexistence or positive solutions in the place, the real reality remains biased to one of the parties by being able and dominant at the expense of the other party. In the first section, the text highlights for us a class jostling leading to the exploitation of the element the White (White man) for the potential of the black element (black man), which leads eventually to black AnshakAnzoaih towards the margin. As for the second syllable, it tells us another interaction between coal (black) and smoke (white), which results in the sublimation of smoke and its rise to the top with regard to the coal's base, its decay, and its decay at the bottom. As for the third syllable, it provides us with another form of crowding, represented by the struggle for existence between (white and black). In his father's head he lived (black hair), but by the guest's ability (white hair) he started to expel black hair. This means that there is a contradiction between two different positions, the first is the position of the black, which is compatible with the other, and it is positive in its essence, while the other is represented by the position of the white that is repelling to the other, it is negative in its essence, and here the textuality of the text returns to the beginning, since the black was a productive, sacrificing factor ... etc. As for white, it was a lazy (nap), a negative stimulus, the idea that the text was keen to present from its title until its end, the idea that can be summarized as a kind of negative exploitation leading to the melting of one of the poles of the powder (black) equation, and reducing it to the other (white) dominant It is an algebraic situation in place.

References

- Methodology - a theoretical introduction and an applied study, d. Fathallah Suleiman, Cairo, 1990.
- Complete Poetic Works, Ahmad Matar, London edition, 2003.
- Characteristics of the method in Shawqiyat, d. Mohamed HadiTrabelsi, Tunisian University Publications, 1981.
- The space of the text - the critical possible in the modern poetic text, Dr. Abdul-Azim Al-Sultani, International Center for Studies and Research 5- The Green Book, Libya, i 1, 2006.
- The High Language, Jean Cohen, translated by Dr. Ahmed Darwish, The Higher Council for Culture and Arts, Cairo, 1995: 187.
- Receiving theory, principles and applications, d. Bushra Musa Salih, General Cultural Affairs House, Baghdad, 1st edition, 1999.
- The place in the poetry of Mahmoud Darwish, Hassan Ghanem Al-Janabi, PhD thesis submitted to the Council of the College of Education, University of Babylon / 2011.
- The Complete Poetic Works, Ahmad Matar, London edition 2003: 304.
- Facilitating the text - the possibility of criticism in the modern poetic text, Dr. Abd al-Azim al-Sultani, International Center for Studies and Research on the Green Book, Libya, i 1, 2006: 7.
- Looking, M. N: 12.
- Looking, Theory of Receipt, Origins and Applications, d. Bushra Musa Saleh, General Cultural Affairs House, Baghdad, 1st edition, 1999: 65.
- Looks, the characteristics of the thing in Alshoukiat, d. Mohamed El HadiTraboulsi, Tunisian University Publications, 1981: 98.
- Looks, and immediate _ a theoretical entrance and applied study, d. Fathallah Suleiman, Cairo, 1990: 53.
- Looking, High Language, Jean Cohen, translated by Dr. Ahmed Darwish, The Higher Council for Culture and Arts, Cairo, 1995: 187.
- Looking at m. N: 181-182.
- The place looks at the poetry of Mahmoud Darwish, Hassan Ghanem Al-Janabi, PhD thesis submitted to the Council of the College of Education, University of Babylon: 53, 59.

Author Information

Prof. Dr. Hassan Ghanem Fadala Al-Janabi

College of Basic Education, University of Babylon,
Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific
Research, Ira
